

Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.

Deliverable Title: **D4.3 Collection of the individual action plans of the three territories**

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Lead beneficiary: **Montanuniversitaet Leoben, MUL**

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Description of the deliverable (3-5 lines)	The territorial action plans based on the objectives developed in Task 4.2 and described in D4.2 are described. In each territory, nine of the actions are planned to be implemented with Oct 2021. Three further actions follow till December 2022.
Key words	Actions for digital transition; RRI implementation; cross-territorial events.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

DigiTeRRI elaborates a framework and a roadmap for transforming territories with traditional industry history into digitalised R&I ecosystems. It implements actions in a participatory process for managing the challenges set by the interplay between science and society of the three territories engaged (Värmland in Sweden, Grand Est in France, and Styria in Austria). The RRI approach (i.e., gender equality, science education, open access/open data, public engagement, and ethics) supports this transition process by implementing adequate RRI strategies into the regional policies. The establishment of self-sustaining R&I ecosystem will be supported by anticipative and participative concepts by taking into account inclusiveness and openness. The three territories bring in their different cultures as well as their common history and experience in traditional industry. Transnational cross-learning is ensured by several highly structured workshops in each territory with participants of the other territories.

Deliverable D 4.3 summarizes the planned activities of the three territories Styria, Värmland, and Grand Est, the territorial action plans. The activities are derived from the roadmap objectives described in Deliverable D4.2 Report on the three build roadmaps. The territorial roadmaps for digital transformation have been developed a regional roadmap together with their stakeholders as part of the DigiTeRRI project. These roadmaps address both the objectives for the next five years and the possible packages of measures that needs to be implemented to achieve the regional objectives and derived goals. The goals and objectives are aligned with the vision statements. The vision statements and roadmap objectives were developed in several workshops with stakeholders in the DigiTeRRI territories. The planned activities will be key to be implemented into strategic plans in the territories.

Deliverable D4.3 is a compilation of all planned activities to be implemented in the period from October 2021 to the end of the project in December 2022. In July 2022, the majority of the implemented activities will be evaluated in order to obtain a comprehensive overview of the state of the transition to digitisation. In principle, activities will be implemented and documented until the end of the project. Each territory has to plan and implement at least nine activities in the monitoring period until July 2022. In addition, three further initiatives per region are to be implemented by the end of the project.

The actions and their implementation are based on the applied RRI approach, where stakeholders in an anticipatory, transparent, and diverse process adapt the current situation to the necessary change also by addressing ethics, gender equality, open access, science education, and engaging the public.

1 INTRODUCTION

The DigiTeRRI project is developing a framework and roadmap for a responsible transition of traditional industrial regions into digitalised industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems using the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach. The co-creation of the framework, the roadmapping process and the implementation of the actions is done with partners and their stakeholders from three areas in Europe, Värmland in Sweden, Région Grand Est in France and Steiermark in Austria. The project addresses the complexity of challenges in the interaction of science, economy, government and society in the defined territories. Multi-stakeholders from the three partner territories are involved in this project.

Deliverable D4.3 is the planning and documentation of the actions to be implemented in the Phase D (Figure 1) of the DigiTeRRI project. Starting from the formulated roadmap objectives and measures each of the territories derives their individual actions. These actions can consist of several initiatives that build a small project. Each activity must relate to the defined objective and outcome of the roadmap. Some are focused on the individual regions, but others can be territorial actions so that there is a benefit for each region through trans-territorial cooperation. Activities can be studies, events, networking, or the development of concepts to achieve a specific purpose within the territorial roadmap.

Figure 1: Scheme of strategic roadmapping in DigiTeRRI.

The roadmaps were elaborated for seven specific roadmap domains, knowledge & skills, technology, networks & collaboration, infrastructure, culture & values, leadership, business & market, communication, as described in the Deliverables D3.2 and D4.2. The roadmaps follow a specific logic, also described in detail in D4.2, however repeated here for easier readability. DigiTeRRI understands the goals, objectives, gaps, milestones, actions, and measures as presented in the following table

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(**Table 1: Logic items of a roadmap.**)¹. These goals, objectives, etc. follow, of course, the vision, developed beforehand (Deliverable D3.3).

Table 1: Logic items of a roadmap.

Logic Item ²	Description
<i>Goals:</i>	The goals are a clear and concise set of targets that, if achieved, will result in the desired outcome. In management literature, sometimes, there is a distinction between a “goal” and an “objective”. A goal can be somewhat abstract and provides a big picture. A goal defines the general intentions and ambitions, however, can be difficult to measure.
<i>Objectives:</i>	Once a core goal is set, defining objectives is the next step towards fostering a clear understanding of how to reach the desired outcome. The main difference between objectives and goals is that objectives cover precise actions including measurable steps individuals and groups take to move closer to the goal. They are specific targets that typically have a time-bound schedule or timeline for completion. <i>(For example, a company may have a goal of becoming the most profitable advertising agency in the country. Objectives related to this goal might include increasing their new business sales by five percent each quarter, growing their market share by a set time frame, improving client retention rates by 10 percent each month or adding two new products to their product line by the end of the fiscal year.³)</i>
<i>Milestones:</i>	Milestones are interim performance targets for achieving the goals with specific dates (e.g., “50% of the municipalities will have built the hardware for high-speed internet by Oct. 2021”).
<i>Gaps and barriers:</i>	The roadmap

¹ International Energy Agency. (2014). Energy Technology Roadmaps: A Guide to Development and Implementation. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264086340-en>.

² International Energy Agency. (2014). Energy Technology Roadmaps: A Guide to Development and Implementation. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264086340-en>.

³ <https://www.samewave.com/posts/the-difference-between-goals-and-objectives-create-an-actionable-business-planning-process>

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Logic Item ²	Description
	<p>process will detect a list of potential gaps in knowledge, technology limitations, market, structural barriers, regulatory limitations, public acceptance, or other barriers to achieving the goals and milestones.</p>
<i>Actions:</i>	<p>The actions are developed to overcome any gaps or barriers. Actions are measures to overcome obstacles, to pave the way for achieving the goals. Typical solution actions include technology development, development of regulations and standards, policy agendas, creation of financing mechanisms, and public engagement.</p>
<i>Priorities and timelines:</i>	<p>The actions will be prioritised with timelines. The most important actions that need to be taken to achieve the goals and the time frames will be specified. There will be interconnections among those actions. These interconnections must be carefully considered with regard to the affected stakeholder roles and relationships.</p>
<i>Measures</i>	<p>Measures are a plan or course of action taken to achieve a particular purpose ⁽⁴⁾ ⁽⁵⁾. Examples are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “It said cost-cutting measures and cost control remain the focus for more than one-third of organisations in 2004.” ○ “Another measure planned will allow for cross-investments between sub-funds run by the same fund manager.” ○ “The company has already said it will take a restructuring charge this year due to cost-cutting measures in its operations.” ○ “Banks will also be asked to draw up measures to achieve gender equality and agree a plan for achieving targets.” ○ “It added that these international players have started initiating cost-cutting measures to improve their cost-structure.” ○ “The Green Party’s new election manifesto contains a programme of realistic, mutually consistent and self-reinforcing measures to achieve localisation.”

⁴ Definitions from Oxford Languages

⁵ <https://www.lexico.com/definition/measure>

2 ACTION PLAN

The action plan is a collection of the derived actions of the three territories in implementing the stakeholder-oriented roadmaps. Each action has to be described by the following items:

A short name, a short description of the action itself, persons, and organisation in charge of performing the action, relation of the action to objectives and measures in the roadmap, information about targeted stakeholders or involved stakeholders, and a short project sketch of the implementation of action.

Important is also to highlight if the action has a cross regional character or not. For each action, a starting point and the duration of the implementation have to be given. Each action has to contribute to close the gap towards a RRI oriented digitalisation of the three territories. (See Appendix 1 – table for collection of the actions.)

3 PROCESS FOR SELECTION OF ACTIONS

Based on the co-created vision statement and the roadmap goals and objectives in each territory, which were elaborated in several stakeholder workshops, a plan for implementing actions had to be developed. According to this plan each territory has the responsibility to decide on the actions and which actions that will be priorities for the first year of implementation. In general, no requirements on the nature of the actions were given. Outcome of the action planning was triggered by the urgency of the actions with respect to the implementation and the resources for realisation. The three territories had free selection of the objective or developed measures and in deriving the actions. The selection of the actions has to follow a multi-actor decision making process. Suggestions for cross regional actions were introduced to the other territorial partners. In an open decision, making procedure it was agreed which actions will be followed by all partners of the DigiTeRRI consortium.

4 NUMBER OF THE ACTIONS

The DoW⁶ in DigiTeRRI foresees that each territorial consortium team has to implement twelve different actions in the period October 2021 to December 2022. Nine of them have to be evaluated by the end of

⁶ Description of Work (based on the DigiTeRRI Proposal)

July 2022 in order to get an overview of the state of implementation so that lessons can be learned from the evaluations of the transformation process.

5 ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED ACTIONS

In the following chapter an analysis of the type of the actions is completed so that an implementation profile for each territory is derived. In table on the number of the action per territory are summarised. The DoW foresees the implementation of at least 9 actions until project month 32 to be evaluated afterwards, and three further actions till the end of the project.

Table 2: Number of actions per region.

Territory	Actions till July 2022	Actions till December 2022
Värmland	9	14
Grand Est	9	12
Styria	9	15

In order to obtain a characterisation of the planned actions, they were divided into the following groups:

- Studies / statement papers/surveys (will be measured by number of documents)
- Events / workshops / conferences / trainings (will be measured by number of events and optional number of attendees)
- Concepts / projects /support (will be measured by number of concepts, project and support actions)
- Networking (will be measured by people being involved) or
- Cross regional actions (will be measured by number of actions, people involved and European territorial outreach).

Some actions can be classified in more than one category, especially networking. The category cross regional action is selected to highlight the interrelation and cooperation of the three territories. The results of that analysis of actions are summarized in (**Table 3:** *Type of actions.*)

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Table 3: Type of actions.

Type of action ⁷	Värmland	Grand Est	Styria
Studies/Statement papers	33%	10.5%	4%
Event/Workshop/Conference/trainings	22%	21.0%	34%
Concept development/project development/ Support	17%	16.0%	24%
Networking	17%	32.0%	10%
Media material / media interaction	0	5.0%	4%
Challenges / awards	0	5.0%	0
Cross regional actions	11%	10.5%	24%

During the planning of the action, the RRI orientation was also surveyed, see **Table 4: Relation to RRI processes or RRI keys in the defined actions.** The following table shows the RRI orientation of the planned actions.

Table 4: Relation to RRI processes or RRI keys in the defined actions.

RRI ⁸ action	Värmland	Grand EST	Styria	All
Actions have RRI key orientation	62%	48%	75%	61%
Actions have RRI Process orientation	38%	52%	25%	39%

Grand Est has a balanced RRI orientation on RRI keys and RRI processes. Styria and Värmland, on the other hand, put emphases on the RRI keys rather than RRI process orientation. In general, for the

⁷ One action can have different type characteristics e.g., it can be networking action and also an event.

⁸ RRI processes are characterised as anticipative, transparent, adaptive to change, and diverse and inclusive. RRI keys are ethics, gender equality, science education, open access, and public engagement.

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entire DigiTeRRI project teams, the orientation towards RRI keys is significantly stronger than the RRI process orientation.

Table 5: Stakeholder and actions.

Stakeholder Groups	Värmland	Grand EST	Styria	All
Education/research organisation	31%	30%	30%	30%
Industry & business	35%	25%	22%	27%
Public authorities, politician	17%	17%	25%	20%
Societal representing, organisations/ media	17%	29%	23%	23%

Table 5 shows the intended engagement of the stakeholder types according to the definition within the DigiTeRRI project (stakeholder coming from science & research, education, industry & business, public authorities, and civil society). In principle the definition follows the idea of the quadruple helix innovation ecosystem, whereas here in DigiTeRRI also education is addressed. For all territories the average engagement of stakeholder groups provides a fair distribution. Värmland has a slightly strong action plan in direction of business and industry, Grand Est and Styria have similar profiles. Grand Est has a bit more pronounced focus on societal representing organisations, whereas Styria shows a stronger planned interaction with public authorities and politicians.

For each territory a profile of the action with respect to their defined objectives and planned measures are given. That analysis has to be done individually per territory because the stakeholder approach and the different status of digitalisation lead to different priorities with respect to objectives and measures.

6 ACTION PLANS OF THE THREE TERRITORIES

6.1 Värmland – Action Plan

The Värmland territory developed 14 action with 10 regional actions and some cross-regional activities with Grand EST and Styria.

Table 6: Purpose of objective according to dimension in roadmap (Värmland).

Type of dimension	Main objectives according to the roadmap
Knowledge and skills	Allow for collaborative approaches for the development, sharing and utilisation of knowledge and skills.
Networks and collaboration	Explore the purpose of networks and connecting them across traditional boundaries to disrupt silo thinking and approaches.
Culture and values	Provide the opportunities for a deeper engagement with civil society and ensuring that their perspective is embedded in BOTH policy and strategy at the regional level. Raising the RRI perspective in the working and thinking of the sectors that has potentials for development and transformation of a traditional industrial region into a digitalised region.
Leadership, business, and market	Provide opportunities from research and the business sector to collaborate in developing leadership training that incorporate RRI and digitalisation. This alongside the potential to global markets and business.
Communication	Create awareness within the wider society of RRI and digitalisation as well as a promotion of the attractiveness of the region.

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Table 7: Target activities of the territory of Värmland.

Activities according to the roadmap	Targeted action
Provide the opportunity for discussion, training across sectors in relation to data management and stewardship	Understand the legislative and RRI perspective in relation to how we deal with data management and stewardship and connect this to the open science context
Grow networks and the contact between networks to foster a joint up approach to digitalisation and RRI	Chose a number of networks to directly engage with and facilitate the organisation of the gathers while allows the participants to set and drive the agendas so ownership lies with the network.
Provide a platform for relevant policy and strategy development with analyse of policy and it impact. In particular the Smart Specialisation strategy and Regional development strategy.	Use the Smart specialisation, the regional development and the regional digitalisation strategies as tools for introducing RRI and digitalisation in a horizontal manner. Transport the method within DigiTeRRI to others as a tool for working with smart specialisation.
Provide opportunities for transnational learning and engagement through selected and targeted activities.	Sharing approaches and practices Promote elements of RRI openness, transparency, as well as inclusiveness.

Table 8: Objectives and actions (*) Värmland).

(*) some actions fit into more than one Categories of objective

Categories of objective	Fraction of actions addressing field of activities according to the roadmap
Working across the traditional silos	27%
Data and open science	20%
Digitalisation and RRI with Structures and training	27%
Territory Attractiveness	13%
Sharing and gaining knowledge transnationally	13%

6.1.1 The detailed action plan for Värmland

In the following the actions of Värmland are described in detail.

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Action No 1: Apply the competence wheel (compare methodology)

Name of action	Apply the competence wheel (compare methodology)
Date (week or month)	October 2021
Location (physical/web, event side)	Digitally - (Teams/Zoom)
Description of the action:	<p>A well proven methodology called Competence Wheel will be used to identify the competence gap as well as the future needs from the industry and the possibilities that are coming with new technology.</p> <p>https://www.compare.se/uploads/2020/02/Kompetenshjulet.pdf</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Industry and business
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	No

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Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Knowledge and Skills / high level data management courses
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Competence mapping, gaps identification, future needs
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation Q3 2021 and performed during October 1st – 31st.
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Low data management capabilities and capacities on high level data science management currently.
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Investigate companies' needs for data science. Investigate companies', and public sector's needs for open data
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Anticipative initiative, Science Education
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single

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Action No 2: Use competence-wheel

Name of action	Use competence-wheel to investigate the needs of open data and data science within companies.
Date (week or month)	Q4 2021
Location (physical/web, event side)	Digitally - (Teams/Zoom)
Description of the action:	Together with stakeholders, Cluster, Academia and companies, meetings will be held to identify the needs from the industry. The academia will present the content in their courses and industry will present the competence gap they have.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Industry and Business
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Computer Science at Karlstad university, Uddeholm, BillerudKorsnäs, Stora Enso, Nordic Paper, Volvo Equipments.
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Knowledge and Skills / high level data management courses

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Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Investigate companies' needs for data science. Investigate companies', and public sector's needs for open data
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation October 2021, performed Nov.-Dec. 2021.
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Low data management capabilities and capacities on high level data science management currently.
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Survey to the education providers
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Anticipative initiative, Science Education
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Multiple
	1 Start-up meeting for stakeholders, discussing the needs and next step
	2 In depth discussions on stakeholder needs

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3	Conduct a mapping to validate needs broadly for industry and delivery capabilities among education providers
4	Development of courses based on the identified needs.

Action No 3: Mapping of solutions in use

Name of action	Mapping which solutions that are in use today
Date (week or month)	Q1 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Digitally and physically
Description of the action:	Mapping which solutions that are in use today
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Business & Industry

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Clusters and companies
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Technology/Develop methods and tools for instructions and manuals with digital technics
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Survey to the education providers
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation Q4 2021 and performed Q1 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Digital technics are used in smaller scales and there is a lack of coordination between companies which hinders efficient implementation.
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures? –	Conduct a survey to validate needs broadly
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Anticipative and open access
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single

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Action No 4: Survey on the future needs

Name of action	Survey the future needs which do not have solutions today
Date (week or month)	Q1 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Digitally and physically
Description of the action:	Survey the future needs which do not currently have solutions
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Business & Industry
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Clusters and companies
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Technology/Develop methods and tools for instructions and manuals with digital technics
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Conduct a survey to validate needs broadly

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Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation Q4 2021 and performed Q1 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Digital technics are used in smaller scales and there is a lack of coordination between companies which hinders efficient implementation.
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Design educational/training modules
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Anticipative and open access
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single

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Action No 5: Design offers and services

Name of action	Design offers and services that are available between companies.
Date (week or month)	Q2 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Digitally and physically
Description of the action:	Design offers and services that are available between companies.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Business & Industry
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Clusters and companies
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Technology/Develop methods and tools for instructions and manuals with digital technics
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Design educational/training modules

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Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation Q4 2021 and performed Q2 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Digital technics are used in smaller scales and there is a lack of coordination between companies which hinders efficient implementation.
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	No
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Anticipative and open access
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single

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Action No 6: Digital Data Stewardship Course

Name of action	Digital Data Stewardship Course
Date (week or month)	Q1 2022 – Q3 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Web
Description of the action:	Provide a data stewardship course for researchers, public bodies and business sector
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Karlstad University (Grants and Innovation Office) Eamonn McCallion, James Lees & Sofia Andersson
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Business & Industry, Research & Science and Public Sector
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Karlstad University and Clusters
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Leadership and Competence and Knowledge
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Low data management capabilities and capacities on high level data science management currently.

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Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	January 2022 – June 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	No current joined-up approach to data stewardship.
Does that action support other goals?	Networking
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	N/A
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	RRI Governance, Ethics & Open access
Is that a cross territorial action?	NO, but could be
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Multiple
	1 Review the DOCENHACE Course and engage with the developers
	2 Make changes within the course to open it to the wider stakeholder group
	3 Run the course

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Action No 7: Territorial attractiveness of Värmland

Name of action	Territorial attractiveness of Värmland
Date (week or month)	
Location (physical/web, event side)	The events will be hybrid to engage as many stakeholders as possible
Description of the action:	Territorial attractiveness of Värmland, and that as part of the further internationalisation of Värmland based business. A hybrid conference on RRI and digitalization.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Region Värmland, Karlstad University
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Business & Industry, public bodies, research and science and Civil society
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	TBC
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	To ensure that digitalisation is part of the driving force of the territorial attractiveness of Värmland, and that as part of the further internationalisation of Värmland based business in order to attract more employment opportunities as well as enhancing work-life balance within the territory.

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Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Domains: Network & Collaboration, Knowledge and competence
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	February 2022 – June 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Enhance the co-ordination and joined-up approaches between stakeholders in addressing digitalisation, i.e., less of a silo approach when addressing the digitalisation needs of the stakeholders in a global market. To further provide opportunities to SMEs so that they can easier access the global market in new ways as a result of digitalisation maturity process.
Does that action support other goals?	Communication and regional attractiveness
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	N/A
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Gender Equality, Public engagement
Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Multiple

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1	Identification of the key stakeholder group that can drive and respond to the goal
2	Communicate and engagement with the stakeholders
3	Carry out a more detailed audit of how the territorial leadership, i.e. the political level, business community, research and science sectors, and public bodies, can maximise the potential of digitalisation for the whole of the territory.
4	For the leadership to provide the meeting places where the various strategies for Värmland can be synergised and utilised by all stakeholders.

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Action No 8: Digitalisation and RRI in Leadership Training

Name of action	Digitalisation and RRI in Leadership Training
Date (week or month)	Q1 2022 – Q3 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical
Description of the action:	Develop and deliver a Leadership Course for researchers that includes the leadership in the digital era and RRI within leadership and research.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Karlstad University
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Research & Science
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	No
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Develop and deliver a Leadership Course for researchers that includes the leadership in the digital era and RRI within leadership and research.

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Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Domain, knowledge and skills, Leadership, culture
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	November 2021 – May 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Leadership training for researchers and the specifics of research leadership is not currently delivered and does not incorporate the need to link to the external environment beyond the university.
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures	Promote and communicate the challenges and the possibilities and ensure gender perspectives;
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	gender equality, science education, public engagement, ethics, giving open access, RRI governance
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Multiple
1	Gather an implementation Group

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2	Develop the curriculum
3	Pilot the course

Action No 9: Compilation of analytical reports and studies

Name of action	Compilation of analytical reports and studies including 2.3 and 2.4 DigiTeRRI
Date (week or month)	Start Q4 2021 stop Q2 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	www.regionvarmland.se
Description of the action:	Compilation of findings of reports and studies. Draw conclusions on the digital divide, social contract, and the effects on citizenship in the context of citizenship through RRI lenses
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Anders Olsson and Helen Vogelmann, Region Värmland
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Innovation actors in the innovation system: Companies

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	Universities Civil society and NGO's
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Companies Universities Civil society and NGO's
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Close the digital divide and the social contract and citizenship.
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Continuous development of Triple helix and Communication with municipalities and NGOs so as to be able to design a digitalisation plan for the territory of Värmland. The gaps in different reports and analyses need to be compiled and from them different actions derived.
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Q2 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Region Värmland has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related. The gaps in different reports and analyses need to be compiled and from them different actions derived.

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<p>Does that action support other goals?</p>	<p>Short: Start work with digitalisation strategy connected to the smart specialisation strategy 2022-2027.</p> <p>Long: Co-create in Q4 digital transformation strategy.</p>
<p>Does that action support the realisation of other measures?</p>	<p>Deepened dialogue with the cluster organisations to start form a business plan for DIGI-Värmland 2022-2027.</p> <p>DIGI-Värmland Q3 2022 – strategy and financial plan</p> <p>Utilise the Academy for Smart Specialisation.</p> <p>First event to be held at CCC based on Regional Development Strategy and the new Smart Specialisation Strategy Co-creation with users and competence networks like older generations, disabled, together with Värmland platform social innovation.</p> <p>Q3 2021- Q4 2027 part of regional broadband plan and the regional digitalisation plan with the goal to cover at least 90% of the territory that is part of the smart specialisation strategy 2021-2027.</p>
<p>Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?</p>	<p>Reflective</p> <p>Addresses gender equality, public engagement, ethics and RRI governance</p>

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Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	Learning and exchange of next practices within the smart specialisation strategies incorporating digital transformation from an RRI framework
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

Action No 10: Hiring of digital coordinator

Name of action	Hiring of digital coordinator Q3 2022
Date (week or month)	Start Q2 2021 stop Q3 2021
Location (physical/web, event side)	www.regionvarmland.se
Description of the action:	Hiring regional digital coordinator and transfer knowledge and incorporate the expert into the DigiTeRRI work from Q4 2021
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Anders Olsson and Helen Vogelmann
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Innovation actors in the innovation system: Companies

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	Universities Civil society and NGO's Region Värmlands internal digital transformation
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Companies Universities Civil society and NGO's
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Close the digital divide and the social contract and citizenship.
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	One of the important tools is the Regional Development Plan 2040. Another important part is the hiring of a digitalisation coordinator and a digitalisation plan for Värmland.
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Q2 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Region Värmland has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related.
Does that action support other goals?	Short: Start work with digitalisation strategy connected to the smart specialisation strategy 2022-2027.

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	Long: Co-create in Q4 digital transformation strategy.
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	<p>Deepened dialogue with the cluster organisations to start form a business plan for DIGI-Värmland 2022-2027.</p> <p>DIGI-Värmland Q3 2022 – strategy and financial plan</p> <p>Utilise the Academy for Smart Specialisation.</p> <p>First event to be held at CCC based on Regional Development Strategy and the new Smart Specialisation Strategy Co-creation with users and competence networks like older generations, disabled, together with Värmland platform social innovation.</p> <p>Q3 2021- Q4 2027 part of regional broadband plan and the regional digitalisation plan with the goal to cover at least 90% of the territory that is part of the smart specialisation strategy 2021-2027.</p>
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Responsive, addresses gender equality, public engagement, ethics and RRI governance
Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	N/A
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

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Action No 11: Digitalisation and S3

Name of action	Digitalisation as part of the smart specialisation strategy of Region Värmland – Q3 2021 to Q4 2021 as well as financial strategy and plan Q4 2021 to Q1 2022
Date (week or month)	Start Q2 2021 stop Q1 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	www.regionvarmland.se
Description of the action:	Working with the regional steering groups, civil servants and politicians to ensure the horizontal theme of digitalisation is informed by the DigiTeRRI project and embedded into the relevant strategies.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Anders Olsson and Helen Vogelmann
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Innovation actors in the innovation system: Companies Universities Civil society and NGO's Region Värmlands internal digital transformation

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<p>If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation</p>	<p>Companies Universities Civil society and NGO's</p>
<p>Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap</p>	<p>Close the digital divide and the social contract and citizenship.</p>
<p>Name the group of measure to which the action contributes</p>	<p>Communications campaign about the possibilities of digitalisation and international communication with focus on digitalisation in Värmland.</p>
<p>Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)</p>	<p>Q2 2022</p>
<p>Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap</p>	<p>Region Värmland has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related.</p>
<p>Does that action support other goals?</p>	<p>Short: Start work with digitalisation strategy connected to the smart specialisation strategy 2022-2027. Long: Co-create in Q4 digital transformation strategy.</p>

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<p>Does that action support the realisation of other measures? –</p>	<p>Deepened dialogue with the cluster organisations to start form a business plan for DIGI-Värmland 2022-2027.</p> <p>DIGI-Värmland Q3 2022 – strategy and financial plan</p> <p>Utilise the Academy for Smart Specialisation.</p> <p>First event to be held at CCC based on Regional Development Strategy and the new Smart Specialisation Strategy Co-creation with users and competence networks like older generations, disabled, together with Värmland platform social innovation.</p> <p>Q3 2021- Q4 2027 part of regional broadband plan and the regional digitalisation plan with the goal to cover at least 90% of the territory that is part of the smart specialisation strategy 2021-2027.</p>
<p>Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?</p>	<p>Responsive</p> <p>Addresses gender equality, public engagement, ethics and RRI governance</p>
<p>Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Is it a single action or multiple actions</p>	<p>Single action</p>

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Action No 12: Digitalisation and S3 – expansion to Dalarna

Name of action	Digitalisation as part of the smart specialisation strategy expanded to Region Dalarna with the use of methodology and knowledge from DigiTeRRI project
Date (week or month)	Start Q4 2021 stop Q2 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	www.regionvarmland.se
Description of the action:	Working with the regional actors within the regional governance framework in Dalarna to design and deliver a DigiTeRRI light that will contribute to their smart specialisation strategy
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Anders Olsson and Helen Vogelmann as well as Eva Lundin
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Innovation actors in the innovation system: Companies Universities Civil society and NGO's Region Värmlands internal digital transformation

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<p>If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation</p>	<p>Companies Universities Civil society and NGO's</p>
<p>Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap</p>	<p>Close the digital divide and the social contract and citizenship.</p>
<p>Name the group of measure to which the action contributes</p>	<p>Dialogue with NGO's, municipalities, companies, exchange of experiences; Design toolbox and inspiration box for attractive places; Analyse maturity levels and needs; Design new forms of learning – bootcamps etc.;</p>
<p>Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)</p>	<p>Q3 2022</p>
<p>Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap</p>	<p>Region Dalarna has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related.</p>
<p>Does that action support other goals?</p>	<p>Short: Start work with digitalisation strategy connected to the smart specialisation strategy 2022-2027. Long: Co-create in Q4 digital transformation strategy.</p>

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<p>Does that action support the realisation of other measures?</p>	<p>Transfer knowledge and methods from Värmland to Dalarna regarding:</p> <p>Deepened dialogue with the cluster organisations to start form a business plan for DIGI-Värmland 2022-2027.</p> <p>DIGI-Värmland Q3 2022 – strategy and financial plan</p> <p>Utilise the Academy for Smart Specialisation.</p> <p>First event to be held at CCC based on Regional Development Strategy and the new Smart Specialisation Strategy Co-creation with users and competence networks like older generations, disabled, together with Värmland platform social innovation.</p> <p>Q3 2021- Q4 2027 part of regional broadband plan and the regional digitalisation plan with the goal to cover at least 90% of the territory that is part of the smart specialisation strategy 2021-2027.</p>
<p>Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?</p>	<p>Responsive</p> <p>Addresses gender equality, public engagement, ethics and RRI governance</p>
<p>Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Is it a single action or multiple actions</p>	<p>Single action</p>

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Action No 13: Interaction and exchange with other student Unions

Name of action	Interaction and exchange with other student Unions of the DigiTeRRI territories
Date (week or month)	Q4 2021
Location (physical/web, event side)	Digital Online
Description of the action:	<p>To support the cross regional networking from the student's side, ideas on studies, students' cooperation using digital means and perspectives will be shared among the students taking part in the project.</p> <p>This way, students can work on strategies on how to publish the results of the roadmap to the other students and how to arise interest for events.</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	<p>Action Developed and lead out by</p> <p>ÖH Leoben - Students Union: Julia Brandstetter</p> <p>moderation by Brigitte Kriszt AI/MUL, workshop design</p> <p>Cindy Brätenfeldt Karlstad University and Elvira Skoglund Chair of Karlstad Student Union</p>
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Universities

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Students, young people
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Cross regional networking, higher education
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Identify recourses and funding portfolio; Promote and communicate the challenges and the possibilities; Ensure gender perspectives;
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	January 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Application of digital communication ways for exchange with other students' unions, to derive new ways of networking, new exchange environment, usability of digital territorials networking
Does that action support other goals?	Motivation for students to participate in the project.
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Science education Public engagement

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Is that a cross territorial action	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Action consists of 3 steps
	1 Establishing contact and developing a common agenda – hot topics on digital student exchange – new option of cooperation
	2 Performing the exchange meeting – and outputs, new ideas of exchange
	3 Report of the meeting, analysis and further perspectives, derive option to share results for the project amongst students, evaluation of the action

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Action No 14: Incubator exchange

Name of action	Incubator exchange for fostering entrepreneurship in digitalisation
Date (week or month)	November 2021 –June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Web event
Description of the action:	Develop digital awareness programs and encourage potential founders of their own start-up in a digital environment. Network interface between entrepreneurs with compatible interests and promote or support international market expansion efforts. Promoting digital processes in business management and technical cooperation between companies or expanding digital opportunities to ensure the economic strength of the regions. The cross regional Incubator network supports the development of the digital transformation of the regions through their collaboration and elaboration of risks & opportunities for young companies regarding sustainable growth strategies.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Franz Edler, Centre of Applied Technology Patrik Patrik Bångerijs, Karlstad University
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Economy, research institutes

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Entrepreneurs, Start-ups, incubator
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Leadership, business & market, network and collaboration
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Platform for Networking
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	November 2021 – June 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	The gap of extensive possibility for interaction of incubators
Does that action support other goals?	Cross territory network, communication
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Use the registrar of small businesses in the region and hold an open introduction discussion to identify needs and points of mutual interest directly between the companies and the university.
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed?	Science education, ethics, open access Innovation, public engagement

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Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	Incubators and entrepreneurs of all territories, network and knowledge transfer in all directions
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Multiple Actions
1	Establishing contact and developing a common agenda, promote and organize the event
2	Performing the exchange meeting and seminars
3	Report of the meeting, analysis and further perspectives, derive option to share results for the project, questionnaire to the participants for mapping

6.2 Grand Est – Action Plan

The 12 actions listed below emanate from the work carried out in the framework of the DigiTeRRI roadmap for Grand Est. The actions were generated from ideas and reflections from stakeholders during the 2 workshops led by the Grand Est regional team. The stakeholders were asked to develop a set of actions on the basis of the identified objectives and potential actions. An analysis was done subsequently to the workshops to clearly identify objectives and actions. A call for expression of interest was launched, so that the stakeholders who gave their interest consent in the workshops could participate in the actions.

The Grand Est action plan is following in the objective categories the following main individual objectives.

Table 9: Purpose of objective according to dimension in roadmap (Grand EST).

Type of dimension	Main objectives
Knowledge and skills	<p>Enable all talents to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector</p> <p>Teach new forms of cooperation, increasing social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process</p>
Networks and collaboration	<p>Increase the societal responsibility in process of digital transformation</p> <p>Give as many people of Grand Est to option to discover digital world, giving as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies.</p> <p>Develop new forms of cooperation</p>
Culture and values	<p>Foster the engagement of young females in digitalisation (gender equality)</p> <p>Increase the societal responsibility in process of digital transformation</p>

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Type of dimension	Main objectives
	<p>Give as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies</p> <p>Develop a science culture that acts more regional distributed in the territory, reduce imbalance between urban and rural areas</p>
Leadership, business, and market	Create the conditions for the development of “responsible” digital products and services
Communication	<p>Raise awareness of the opportunities offered by digital sector, enable all talents to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector.</p> <p>Increase social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process.</p> <p>Raise awareness for transition to digitalisation, increasing social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process.</p>

Table 10: Target activities of the territory of Gand Est.

Activities according to the roadmap	Targeted action
Increase the societal responsibility in process of digital transformation	<p>Integration of RRI concepts in the future of European Digital Innovation Hub of Grand Est</p> <p>Develop and implement policies in the process of digital transformation (in funding, in S3)</p>
Enable all talent to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector	<p>Encourage young girls to the digital sector</p> <p>Supporting Citizen in the development of digital projects</p> <p>Forster the engagement of young females in digitalisation</p>

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Creating the conditions for development of “responsible” digital products and services	Sharing best practice Raising awareness
Giving as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies Forster the engagement of young females in digitalisation	Sharing best practice Encourage young girls to the digital sector

Table 11: Objectives and actions.

Categories of objective	Fraction of actions addressing field of activities according to the roadmap
Enable all talent to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector	30% of actions
Giving as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies	15,5% of actions
Increase the societal responsibility in process of digital transformation	30% of actions
Creating the conditions for development of “responsible” digital products and services	15,5% of actions
Develop new forms of cooperation	9 % of actions

6.2.1 The detailed action plan for Grand Est

In the following the actions of Grand Est are described in detail.

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Action No 1: Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub

Name of action	Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub
Date (week or month)	End Q1 (03/2022)
Location (physical/web, event side)	Grand Est schools
Description of the action:	<p>The European Commission will launch end Q3/2022 the Digital Europe Program. A part of the call will be focused on the setting up of one European Digital Innovation Hub per European region. The objective is to accelerate digitalisation of industrial SMEs. The main topics: test before investment, training, funding and networking. The action will be focused on the integration of RRI and especially Inclusion in the activities of EDIH. We will identify different training courses and schools that propose “non-traditional training” (second chance schools,..) and they will be integrated in the future catalogue of training of the EDIH.</p> <p>Activities linked to the setting up of a virtual regional Digital Institute</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Grand E-nov+ / Jean Jacques Bernardini / jj.bernardini@grandenov.plus
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Society, Education Research (Universities, Engineering Schools, Inclusive Schools), Business

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	In our consortium Materialia (cluster) and University of Lorraine are involved – other key stakeholders (Region Grand Est...) are involved.
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	“Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector”
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Acquire digital skills via a tailored training
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	End 2021 (12/21)
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Increase the number of people trained with digital skills, competencies in the digital, increase digitalisation of SMEs by integration of specific skills, increase the number of people trained that could work in companies
Does that action support other goals? Name them	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	No
Which RRI dimension/process/ key are addressed	Reflective process, gender equality, science education

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Is that a cross territorial action	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

Action No 2: Encourage young girls to the digital sector

Name of action	Encourage young girls to hi digital sector
Date (week or month)	October 2021 December 2021
Location (physical/web, event side)	Hybrid
Description of the action:	This is a raising awareness campaign which targeted young girls in secondary schools on the subject of technological and scientific training and professional careers in the digital and industrial sectors through mentoring by women leaders, experts and professionals in the digital field. In order to effectively raise awareness of the importance of RRI and gender equality, the DigiTeRRI Grand Est team will be delivering a series of presentations, during a series of events.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Université de Lorraine, Université, vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr Grand E-Nov+, association, s.toussaint@grandenov.plus

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Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Education Research (colleges, high schools)
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	<p>Society: Elles Bougent lorraine@ellesbougent.com</p> <p>Institutions: Region Grand Est, CCI Alsace Eurométropole</p> <p>Education & Research: Académies de Reims, Nancy-Metz et Strasbourg, high schools</p> <p>Society: Association Robotic Junior Entrepreneurs, Elles Bougent</p> <p>Companies: Batigère</p>
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities offered by the digital sector
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Awareness raising, educational and vocational guidance for women
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	<p>September, October 2021:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of events* <p>Preparation of the contents of the presentations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Logistical and administrative framing <p>October /December 2021:</p>

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	- Presentations
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	<p>Increase the number of applications from young girls for digital-related training and jobs (including in higher education).</p> <p>It is worth noting that more than 300 young female high school students will participate in these actions.</p>
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	No
Which RRI dimension/key are addressed	<p>Anticipative, inclusive processes</p> <p>Gender equality</p> <p>Science education</p>
Is that a cross territorial action	no
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Multiple action
1	<p>Smart City Week</p> <p>14 October 2021</p>

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This event took place in three cities in the Grand Est region: the University of Lorraine in Nancy (ENSGSI) and Metz (ENSAM), as well as the Lycée Technologique in Saint Dié des Vosges.

The action aims to encourage vocations among high school girls for scientific and technological training and careers by presenting them with the professions linked to the SMART CITY or Connected City; What are the Sciences and Technologies at work? What sectors and professions? In concrete terms, what products and services are involved in the companies? For one day, the girls met women executive working in companies in the smart city sector. The programme included: presentation of professions, presentation of RRI, debates and company visits.

In total: 8 high schools participate, 160 girls attended the event, 20 company executives were associated with 8 companies, experts from 7 academic structures (engineering schools) involved, experts from cluster Materialia participated, 2 institutions provided support (Nancy Metropole and Rectorat).

Co-organisers:

- Association « Elles Bougent / Lorraine »
- ENSGSI, Université de Lorraine

Partners:

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	<p>BATIGERE, BLUE PAD, DALKIA, NUMALLIANCE, RTE, VINCI CONSTRUCTION, SPIE and Matéria (cluster from the DigiTeRRI team)</p> <p>Academics: ENSAM - ENSGSI - EI-CESI – ESITC - INSIC - MINES Nancy – Polytech Nancy, High schools (Jean Lurçat de Bruyères, Jacques Callot de Vandoeuvre - Henri Loritz de Nancy - Louis Majorelle de Toul - Alfred Kastler de Stenay - Jean-Auguste Margueritte de Verdun - Louis de Cormontaigne et Lycée de la Communication de Metz) and the Lorraine Fab Living Lab</p> <p>Institutions: Metropole du Grand Nancy, Rectorat</p>
2	<p>Robotech Girls Online</p> <p>Virtual exhibition</p> <p>14 and 15 October 2021</p> <p>Virtual exhibition to raise awareness (inform, discover) among young women in secondary schools about training and professional careers in digital, robotics and technology in order to broaden their choice of orientation to access jobs that are recruiting in many sectors of activity.</p> <p>This event was a virtual fair with the presence of actors and a virtual stand.</p> <p>To learn about the concept of RRI and the project, documents were available on the stand of Grand Enov+ (partner) to present the DigiTeRRI project and an advisor from Grand E-nov+ was also present to inform young women.</p>

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	<p>This exhibition also provided an opportunity to talk to female students, apprentices, alternates or professionals about their career paths, the qualities required and the opportunities in these sectors</p> <p>Partner companies: Hager, Versusmind, Sfereno, Grand E-nov+, Systancia, Clemessy, Emerson, Liebherr, Corteva, Orange, Enedis-RGDF</p>
	<p>3 Event Be Est, Mulhouse</p> <p>1 December 2021</p> <p>Awareness-raising event for young high school girls during the Be Est trade fair (industry of the future) to discover training courses, technologies, industrial players and acquire knowledge about industry and digital technology. It will be an opportunity to discover responsible digital technology from an RRI angle during a conference led by Grand Enov+ on 1st December 2021.</p> <p>Partner companies:</p> <p>https://www.industriesdefutur.eu/fr</p>

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Action No 3: Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)

Name of action	Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)
Date (week or month)	12/2021 (RRI criteria for project selection) and 03/2022 (RRI criteria for project evaluation)
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical meeting could be possible
Description of the action:	<p>The European Commission asked to the Regions to define a Smart Specialisation Strategy that will be annexed to the operational plan (OP) 2021-2027 for ERDF use. Region Grand Est has defined 8 market priorities and 4 transversal priorities. One of those transversal priorities is entitled “responsible innovation”. The objective of the action is to use RRI criteria to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate them in the selection criteria of projects that will be funded. - Integrate them in the follow-up and the evaluation of the performance of the projects funded by the ERDF.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Grand E-nov+ (Jean Jacques Bernardini) and Region Grand Est, Rémi Pierrat, Remi.PIERRAT@grandest.fr
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Policy makers, education research, society

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Region Grand Est
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Increase the societal responsibility in the process of digital transformation
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Develop and implement policies and related strategies to foster responsible digitalisation
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	October 2021 – Two milestones (end 2021 and end of March 2022)
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Integrate Responsible Innovation criteria in the implementation of the next ERDF program (2021-2022) with a focus on innovation activities (link with the S3)
Does that action support other goals? Name them	no
Does that action support the realisation of other measures? – name them	no
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed	Anticipative, reflective, inclusive or responsive initiative Gender equality, science education, public engagement, ethics, giving open access, RRI governance

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Is that a cross territorial action	no
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

Action No 4: RRI criteria for public funding

Name of action	RRI criteria for public funding
Date (week or month)	ongoing
Location (physical/web, event side)	No specific location
Description of the action:	<p>Grand Est region has a strong willingness to help companies in their digital transformation and to launch disruptive projects. Companies (SME, Start-ups, ...) could solicitate different regional funding for their development.</p> <p>Grand E-Nov+ has mobilized to ask for revision and advice to the Grand Est region in order to accept the financing.</p> <p>For this review, we use RRI references as criteria for social impact, ethics and environmental liability</p>

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Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Grand E-Nov+, Alexis Steiner, a.steiner@grandenov.plus
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Policy, business
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Grand Est region
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Increasing social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Develop and implement policies and related strategies to foster responsible digitalisation
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Q1 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	With RRI criteria in the process of funding assignment, we are sure public funding will impact positively our society with responsible innovative projects

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Does that action support other goals?	no
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	no
Which RRI dimension/key are addressed	Reactive, responsive process; Ethical orientation
Is that a cross territorial action	no
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

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Action No 5: Manifesto AI ethical

Name of action	AI ethical Manifesto
Date (week or month)	Document published: summer 2021 Manifesto Promotion: December 2021 Launch event: no defined
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical and web (hybrid version)
Description of the action:	Artificial intelligence is increasingly impacting businesses and people's lives. This new technology raises questions about trust, transparency and ethics. This is why designers of artificial intelligence must take into account the impact on humans in their development. Hence the importance of drafting a reference document that provides a framework and best practices for ethical artificial intelligence. Step one: Production of a document – Guideline for an ethical approach in support of the development artificial intelligence algorithms (http://ai-ethical.com/131-2/) Step two: Disseminating communication elements and promotion of the manifesto in company meetings

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	, virtual stand at the 360 Grand Est event (biggest innovation event in the Grand Est Region) to invite signing the manifesto Step three: Participation in the launch event of the AI Ethical Manifesto and submission to the Secretary of State for the Digital Economy of the French Republic
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Grand E-Nov+, Alexis Steiner, a.steiner@grandenov.plus
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Policy (public authorities), Business
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Grand Enov+, Grand Est region, Numeum (French digital union)
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Creating the conditions for the development of "responsible" digital products and services
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Sharing good practices

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Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	This has already started in August 2021
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	AI solutions developed with RRI-by-design concept, thanks to manifesto AI ethical will have a positive impact on the users and society
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	No
Which RRI dimension/key are addressed	Responsive process, Ethical considerations, giving open access
Is that a cross territorial action	No
IS it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

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Action No 6: Sharing best practices on information search tools

Name of action	Sharing best practices on information search tools
Date (week or month)	Q1/Q2 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical/web
Description of the action:	SMEs, civil society, universities, and research institutions, among other, need to embrace digitalisation and use technological tools. Nevertheless, the tools and methodologies to look for the right information are sometimes unknown. Plus, COVID-19 and fake news have revealed the importance of anticipation and the gathering of good strategic information. The objective is that information search tools are known by the Q-helix stakeholders, so that they can adapt digitalisation.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Materialia, Lucia Gonzalez, lucia.gonzalez@materiaia.fr
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	society, education, research, business

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	LORIA, Laboratory
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Giving as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Sharing best practice
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation action: Q1 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Stakeholders such as SMEs, universities, research institutions and also civil society will learn best practices on information search, providing them with the anticipation and the resilience needed to face new unexpected crisis and embrace digitalisation.
Does that action support other goals	no
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	no
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed	Inclusive process Giving open access

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Is that a cross territorial action	no
Is it a single action or multiple	Single action

Action No 7: RRI awareness-raising video

Name of action	RRI awareness-raising video
Date (week or month)	November 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Web
Description of the action:	In order to raise awareness of the importance of RRI to a wide range of stakeholders of the Quadruple Helix, a video/ series of videos will be developed. The objective is demonstrating different stakeholders the added value represented by RRI and how they can embrace it.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	Materialia, Lucia Gonzalez, lucia.gonzalez@materia.fr , our communications team communication@materia.fr

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Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Education research, policy, business, society
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	WeDo, Mario Magaña mario@wedo-projects.com
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Creating the conditions for the development of 'responsible' digital services and products
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Acculturating the citizen to RRI
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation from mid-September 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Impact: stakeholders need to appropriate RRI terms and methodology and be aware of the positive repercussions when adopting RRI practices.
Does that action support other goals?	Increasing social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	no

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Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed	<p>Inclusive, responsive process</p> <p>Science education, giving open access</p>
Is that a cross territorial action	no
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

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Action No 8: UTTOPIA (technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence)

Name of action	UTTOPIA (technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence) - innovation challenge
Date (week or month)	<p>launch event: 02 December 2021</p> <p>Other actions, in the next 3 years but no dates are known at this time</p>
Location (physical/web, event side)	Forbach, Grand Est region. Possibility of doing it online.
Description of the action:	<p>Plastinnov is launching UTTOPIA, a technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence. In the Forbach territory, an innovative third place will be built, creating synergies between different stakeholders such as the local incubator Eurodev Center – Interface, high schools and a university. As part of the launch of UTTOPIA, an innovation challenge will be launched, providing project holders (different profiles such as unemployed and refugees) with support and technical follow-up by Plastinnov Associate professors (technical profiles keen on factory 4.0 digitalisation) and Materialia. RRI criteria will be taken into account.</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)	<p>Materialia, Lucia Gonzalez lucia.gonzalez@materiaia.fr</p> <p>Plastinnov, Frederic Fradet, frederic.fradet@univ-lorraine.fr</p>

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Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Civil society, SMEs
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Eurodev Center – Interfaces (incubator), IUT SGM, Lycées (Condorcet, Blaise Pascal)
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Supporting citizens in the development of digital projects
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Q1 potential candidates, project holders will be identified Common evaluation criteria will be established A communication campaign will be launched Candidates will be chosen
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Thanks to the innovation challenge, as part of the UTTOPIA initiative, civil society such as unemployed or refugees will embrace digitalisation and learn from new methods and technologies

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Does that action support other goals? Name them	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures? – name them	No
Which RRI dimension/key are addressed	Science education, giving open access
Is that a cross territorial action	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

Action No 9: ICE IAMOT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings

Name of action	ICE IAMOT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings
Date (week or month)	June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Palais des congrès de Nancy

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<p>Description of the action:</p>	<p>This event will bring together researchers, companies and institutions. Several debates are planned on different themes such as digitalization, innovation in local authorities and RRI. Papers from researchers are also scheduled, following a call for papers.</p> <p>This action also plays a major role in terms of communication because many media will be mobilized. Moreover, the best papers will be published in international journals</p>
<p>Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)</p>	<p>ERPI Laboratory and ENSGSI (from Université de Lorraine), Vincent Boly, vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr</p>
<p>Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address</p>	<p>Society, Business, Education Research</p>
<p>If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation</p>	<p>Nancy City Hall</p> <p>The DigiTeRRI partners</p> <p>Association Territoria: association for the promotion of innovation in communities</p> <p>IEEE edition</p> <p>The scientific boards of ICE an IAMOT</p>
<p>Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap</p>	<p>“Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector”</p>

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Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Acculturating to science
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation from September 2021 to June 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Impact: introduce and deepen the concepts of RRI and their impact on the life of citizens and the economy, share some experiences.
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures? – name them	No
Which RRI dimension/key/process are addressed	Inclusive process; Science education, given open access
Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	The DigiTeRRI partners will contribute to the debates during this congress. This will allow a mutualization of knowledge.
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

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Action No 10: Est'ival des Sciences Event

Name of action	Est'ival des Sciences Event
Date (week or month)	From 25 th June until 5 th July 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical
Description of the action:	<p>The EST'ival des Sciences consists of a tour of 10 scientific culture events in rural areas (villages from 700 to 2000 inhabitants), with one event per department in the region.</p> <p>One of the main objectives is to bring science to the general public in "cultural deserts". The main target groups are teenagers (14+) and adults, regardless of their level of education. Scientists from public research laboratories in the region, and start-ups managers whose technology also comes from public research laboratories in the Grand Est, guided by a scientific mediator to help create a friendly atmosphere and make the content accessible to all.</p> <p>These are not conferences, the format is interactive, fun and based on exchanges between the participants and the scientists.</p> <p>The events last around 2 hours and 15 minutes: 15 minutes for the reception of the public, between 1 hour and 1 hour and 30 minutes for the quiz format, 15 to 45 minutes for free discussion with the scientist(s).</p>

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	<p>It was agreed that 2 of the 10 EST'ival des Sciences events would be devoted to digital science themes (in conjunction with Inria or the CNRS). The call for proposals to identify scientific speakers (lecturers, research fellows, doctoral students, etc.) will be launched on 25 October 2021.</p> <p>It is also planned to combine these "theoretical" presentations with the organisation of practical workshops in order to present technologies such as 3D printers, augmented reality, etc. in a concrete manner.</p>
<p>Who is responsible for that the performance of that action (name, organisation, contact mail)</p>	<p>Université de Lorraine, Vincent Boly vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr</p> <p>Association Communicasciences, Anne Vicente, anne.vcte@gmail.com</p>
<p>Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address</p>	<p>Society (population, citizen), education research</p>
<p>If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation</p>	<p>Inria, CNRS : National research institutes</p>
<p>Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap</p>	<p>Giving as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies</p>
<p>Name the group of measure to which the action contributes</p>	<p>Science acculturation</p>

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<p>Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)</p>	<p>October to December 2021: Start of the construction of the pre-programme and partnerships, writing and submission of grant applications</p> <p>January to June 2022: construction of the content of the events, construction of the communication plan and its execution</p>
<p>Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap</p>	<p>A scientific culture that is more widely distributed over the territory: aiming to reduce inequalities in access to scientific culture between urban and rural areas</p>
<p>Does that action support other goals? Name them</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Does that action support the realisation of other measures?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Which RRI dimension/key are addressed</p> <p>Anticipative, reflective, inclusive or responsive initiative</p> <p>Address one of the keys (gender equality, science education, public engagement, ethics, giving open access, RRI governance)</p>	<p>Anticipative</p> <p>Science education</p> <p>Open access</p> <p>Gender equality: showing examples of women in science so that young girls in rural areas are aware that they have a place in science</p>

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Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	No
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Events planned between 25 June and 5 July 2022 during the EST'ival des Sciences, but the dates are not yet fixed.

Action No 11: Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region

Name of action	Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region
Date (week or month)	September 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	The study will investigate the whole Grand Est Region
Description of the action:	The aim is to raise awareness and identify RRI practices in the networks of Fablabs and third places in the Grand Est region. An enquiry will be managed among managers and users of Fab Labs and Third Places of the Region. Their activities, objectives and projects

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	will be confronted to the main principles of RRI. Document will be sent afterwards to the interviewees. A report will be written and published in open access.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Three partners are managing this action: ERPI Laboratory, Archives Poincaré Laboratory and ENSGSI (de l'Université de Lorraine), Laure Morel
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Are involved: FabLabs and third places associations and universities in the region Grand Est.
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	DigiTeRRI partners
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Increasing social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Study / diagnosis of present situation and communication
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	From February to September 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Impact: Assist public decision-makers and project support organizations in taking RRI into account in the strategic decision-making phases of the launching of start-ups and any entrepreneurial activities

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Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures? —	No
Which RRI dimension/key/ are addressed?	Reflective process, public engagement, open access, governance, science education
Is that a cross territorial action?	The enquiry outcomes will be shared with partners.
Is it a single action or multiple actions (add lines for each event) - please describe, which actions will have to follow?	single

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Action No 12: Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops

Name of action	Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops
Date (week or month)	February 2022 and March 2022 May 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Nancy France (February and May 2022) and Värmland Sweden (March 2022)
Description of the action:	Training is organized for company executives simultaneously with students. They all get the same lectures and work together on a specific digital problem of the companies involved.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	ERPI laboratory and ENSGSI (Innovation Engineering Department of the Université de Lorraine)
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Society (Students), education research, business (Start-ups companies, SMEs and global companies)
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	DigiTeRRI partners

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Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Develop new forms of collaboration
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Increasing knowledge and skills
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Agile workshop: preparation from October 2021 to January 2022. A collaboration between Grand Est and Värmland will start in November 2021.
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - diffusion of RRI concepts -increase of the skills of company executives and managers in the field of Agility, - increase of students' skills, - common experience between students and experienced people, - an innovative educational process, <p>Digital summer school: Impacts are the same. A focus will also be made on ethic in research.</p>
Does that action support other goals?	No
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	no
Which RRI dimension/key/ process are addressed	Anticipative, inclusive

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	Public engagement, open access, governance, science education
Is that a cross territorial action?	The Agile workshop will be organized in Grand Est and then the French team will transfer its experience to the Värmland
Is it a single action or multiple actions?	Multi-actions
	<p>1 Agile Workshop: the objective is to organize an annual event in France and in Värmland. In 2022 the events will take place in February (Grand Est) and March (Värmland). During each workshop, three companies will be involved. Executives and student have lectures about agile design approaches, and then collaborate to apply these methodologies to digital development for the companies. Moreover, the challenge of RRI will be detailed to participants. The workshop is three days long.</p>
	<p>2 Digital Summer School: This event in May 2022 is a summer school where 50 PhD and master students works with managers and employees of 2 SMEs/ 1 SME is a French Company and the other one is a French Company. The objective of this 3 days challenge is to transform a traditional SME into an Industry 4.0 SME by taking into account of the digitalization and RRI impacts.</p>

6.3 Styria – Action Plan

In Styria the project team selected the below mentioned actions. In the field of education, a cooperation with stakeholders were established, the students' union was also included here.

In the Styrian roadmap, the following categories of objectives were defined:

Table 12: Dimension of roadmap and objectives.

Type of dimension	Main objectives
Knowledge and skills	Develop skills, extend knowledge, need oriented design training and education programs
Networks and collaboration	Build network and collaboration on any stakeholder level or on cross stakeholder groups for common development initiatives
Technology	Bring new digital technology in research, innovation, and business
Infrastructure	Build up to date and maintain infrastructure
Culture and values	Change mind-set o region to digital natives, raise more awareness for gender equality issues
Leadership, business and market	Let digitalisation become a motor for global growth of tradition technologies offered by the Styrian territory
Communication	Strengthen the image of a modern, economically powerful attractive territories

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From the derived objective five cluster of activities were developed:

Table 13: Target activities of the territory of Styria.

Cluster	Targeted action
Digital Transformation in the field of education	Define and communicate the need for education, build co-operations and exchange.
Cities, municipalities, public sector	Strengthen e governance and offer attractive digital services to the citizens
Technology and knowledge transfer	Sharing of knowledge to develop new digital services and solutions
Creating work- environment and countering the lack of labour force	Change of working condition, new models of cooperation and co-worker sharing, gender equality
A universal platform	Offer a multifunctional platform, giving a digital twin of the territory, build-up of new digital features for citizen and exterritorial public

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The following give the quantitative analysis of the Styrian actions. Table show the relation of the actions to the objective and table that to the targeted activities.

Table 14: Share of actions in the different roadmap dimensions.

Type of dimension	Fraction of actions
Knowledge and skills	23.0%
Networks and collaboration	30.0%
Technology	8.0%
Infrastructure	13.0%
Culture and values	8.5%
Leadership, business, and market	13.0%
Communication	4.5%

6.3.1 The detailed action plan for Styria

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Action No 1: Blackout precautions

Name of action	Blackout precautions
Date (week or month)	11/2021 – ongoing, first initiatives till June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Online / Web Physical information events for municipalities, companies and the population
Description of the action:	<p>The threat of a "blackout" of the energy supply and the associated consequences for communities, the economy and the population seem to be a central issue for the future.</p> <p>In addition to the digital basic supply, this also applies to the decentralized energy supply (to secure basic needs).</p> <p>While larger cities, companies and infrastructure providers are already well prepared here, further support for smaller communities and businesses is required, as well as, of course, comprehensive information for the population.</p> <p>Building on existing knowledge, a broad awareness and information campaign is to be implemented to provide information as extensively and widely as possible.</p> <p>Aim is to increase the resilience against blackout and have stable and robust environment for digitalisation</p>

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Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Erich Weber Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur GesmbH
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Municipalities Companies Infrastructure providers
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Persons responsible for infrastructure measures at the municipal level. Companies Public
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Technology, infrastructure, communication, civil life, work-life balance
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Cities, municipalities, the public sector
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	January 2022 – ongoing in 2022

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Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Creation of an information platform (digital and personal) about the risks associated with a "blackout" and the necessary prerequisites for the best possible management.
Does that action support other goals?	Sustain stable infrastructure for digitalisation in the territory
Does that action support the realisation of other measures	Networking of municipalities, companies and infrastructure providers
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed	Anticipation of future developments, responsiveness action to secure the energy supply of the public and society in the territory.
Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	The topic is definitely an overarching one. The extent to which cross-territorial action is possible here must first be clarified.
Is it a single action or multiple? describe, which actions will have to follow.	Multiple activities
1	General clarification with the municipalities, companies and infrastructure providers.
2	Development of a communication platform (online and physical).
3	Organise meetings and information discussion, perform a simulation game on the blackout scenarios to derive actions plan for the citizen, public administration units and SME

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Action No 2: Exchange of knowledge on digitalisation

Name of action	Exchange of knowledge on digitalisation
Date (week or month)	March – Mai 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical Meeting at Montanuniversitaet
Description of the action:	The mapping of the region and the development of the roadmap gave, that different segments like metallurgy, paper and wood have different levels of implementation of knowledge on digitalisation. Company partners raised the need for an intensified exchange on general new business options by digitalisation. A workshop will start the discussion process of company partner and show first best practices. The workshop should give an impulse for networking and exchange amongst companies
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Brigitte Kriszt, Montanuniversitaet
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Companies
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	No
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Leadership, business & market

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Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Technology and knowledge transfer
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	March – Mai 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Existing knowledge can be exchange, cooperation of companies leads to a broader and homogenous transition process, benefits for regional companies
Does that action support other goals?	Networking, collaboration
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Creating working environment
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Open access
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multipurpose action
1	Finding partner who are reconfirm that they are willing to share their knowledge
2	Planning the workshop event (Date, location, speakers' corner)
3	Performing the event and evaluation of the stakeholder feedback

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Action No 3: Females fit for digitalisation

Name of action	Females fit for digitalisation
Date (week or month)	Nov 2021 – June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Montanuniversitaet, Web meeting – Study and cross regional exchange
Description of the action:	<p>The topic of gender equality was seen as an important issue if it come to new job profiles. Many aspects were raised in the workshops. To have a comprehensive guideline for gender equality recommendation will be given:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange with other partner of the DigiTeRRI project on their finding on gender equality or gender mainstreaming – what best practices are implemented • Analysis what special offers are found in the territory of Styria with respect to transition to digitalisation (initiatives, training, gender equality plan) • Showing the gap – what is needed, giving advice to companies and public authorities • Deriving recommendations
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Brigitte Kriszt, Montanuniversitaet
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Labour services, institutions who offer training programs for females, experts on gender equality and gender equality plans

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	AMS
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Knowledge and Skills, culture and values
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Creating work – environments and countering the lack of skilled labour
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Nov 2021 – Dec 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Awareness for gender equality will help to prevent a gender equality gap in new digital professions
Does that action support other goals?	Communication, leadership
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Universal platform
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Gender equality

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Is that a cross territorial action?	Yes, exchange with Värmland and Grand Est on their best practices to promote females in digitalisation
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multipurpose action
	1 Exchange with other territories, learn about their offers
	2 Analyse the regional offers, and shop gaps and future needs – Workshops
	3 Proposing recommendations
	4 Evaluation of action by questionnaires of involved persons

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Action No 4: MINTernational

Name of action	MINTinternational
Date (week or month)	Start immediately – ongoing
Location (physical/web, event side)	BG BRG Judenburg, Montanuniversitaet, Web
Description of the action:	<p>Transnational exchange should serve as a competence enhancement in the STEM subject canon. To this end, contact with educational institutions in the partner regions is to be sought and established through the DigiTeRRI project. In order to be able to prepare the exchange and formulate common goals, digital tools are to be used and thus anchored even better in everyday school life.</p> <p>The outcomes of Fit4MINt should be included in the European Exchange.</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Prof. Birgit Edlinger-Schauperl (BG BRG Judenburg), Julia Mayerhofer-Lillie (MUL)
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Schools, higher education organisations
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Prof. Birgit Edlinger-Schauperl other international Education organisations

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Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Knowledge and Skills, communication, international networking
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Digital transformation in the field of education
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	1st half year –till end of year 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Cross regional learning, reaching a European dimension on MINT and IT
Does that action support other goals?	Networking and communication
Does that action support the realisation of other measures	Creating work environments and countering lack of skilled labour
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Science education
Is it a single action or multiple?	Cross European action, territories of Värmland and Grand Est are invited to participate
1	Multipurpose action
2	Getting in contact with partners in the initiative – schools and universities,

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3	Preparation of ERASMUS exchange for students and teachers, project work, develop understanding what skill are preferred and needed (aim by the end of the year 2022).
4	Evaluation of change, questionnaire of stakeholder involved

Action No 5: Fit4MINT

Name of action	Schools fit for digitalisation
Date (week or month)	Nov 2021 - June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical Workshop Gymnasium Judenburg
Description of the action:	Educational goals in the STEM area should be clearly defined and communicated between the educational levels and institutions involved. Specifically, attention should be paid to the transition area between AHS and technical university. For this purpose, a networking conference with representatives from both areas should be organised. The university's expectations regarding the educational level of first-year students in the STEM area (specifically the subject's mathematics, physics, chemistry, computer science) are to be communicated and compared with the actual

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	current conditions of the upper secondary school. The aim is to jointly identify possible measures to improve the transition between AHS and university.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Prof. Birgit Edlinger-Schauperl (BG BRG Judenburg), Julia Mayerhofer-Lillie, MUL
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Schools, higher education organisations
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Prof. Birgit Edlinger-Schauperl
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Knowledge and Skills
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Digital transformation in the field of education
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Nov. 2021 – Jun 2022

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Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Close the gap in cooperation between different education organisation on different levels of education
Does that action support other goals?	Networking and collaboration, culture and values, communication
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Networking and cooperation, cities, universal platform
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Science education, Anticipative, reflective, inclusive or responsive initiative
Is that a cross territorial action	No
IS it a single action or multiple actions	Multiple action
1	Preparation of seminar, dissemination, inviting speakers and participants
2	Performing the seminar
3	Analysis the outcomes, communicate the outcomes, questionnaire to the participants

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Action No 6: Awareness of the Styrian Roadmap and initiate resilient transformation

Name of action	Awareness of the Styrian Roadmap and initiate resilient transformation
Date (week or month)	Nov 2022 – June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Web/Physical
Description of the action:	<p>The Roadmap for “Digital Transformation in the upper Styrian Region” was performed with representatives of the stakeholders and members of the core group. In a second phase the current document and the planned actions should be made transparent to all regional stakeholders and organisations in the region. Aim is to increase the contribution on the defined measures and support the realisation of the roadmap in the next 5 years. The dissemination of the roadmap is planned in combination with other defined actions in the action plan, but also by the following activities. Long term aim is to develop the roadmap further.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organising a press conference and introduce the results of the roadmap and the main actions • Printing the roadmap and share it with all relevant companies, cities, schools and research organisation. Public orientated association should also have access to copies of the roadmap. • Introduction of the roadmap at regional events and conferences • Promoting the actions and engage stakeholders in transformation process • Discuss financing for further actions with stakeholders

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Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	MUL, ZAT, Bruck Mur Wirtschaftsentwicklung und Stadtmarketing, WEDO
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	All defined stakeholder groups according to D3.1
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Press, Media, Newspaper, TV
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Communication
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	All defined fields of measures
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Start Nov. 2021 – ongoing action
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Impact is reached by engaging several stakeholders in the transformation process, reaching awareness
Does that action support other goals?	Networking, leadership, culture and values

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Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	No
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Public engagement, open access, initiate and sustain a RRI related transformation process
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multiple actions
	1 Press conference, introduce to the government of Styria
	2 Conference contributions, and talks about the roadmap in DigiTeRRI events
	3 Printed roadmap, spread roadmap amongst territorial stakeholder
	4 Derive financial support and promote actions for transformation, run evaluation and questionnaire about perception of change

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Action No 7: Exchange of Student Unions

Name of action	Interaction and exchange with other student Unions of the DigiTeRRI territories
Date (week or month)	November/December 2021
Location (physical/web, event side)	online
Description of the action:	<p>To support the cross regional networking from the student's side, ideas on studies, student's cooperation using digital means and perspectives will be shared among the students taking part in the project.</p> <p>This way, students can work on strategies on how to publish the results of the roadmap to the other students and how to arise interest for events.</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	ÖH Leoben - Students Union: Julia Brandstetter; moderation by Brigitte Kriszt AI/MUL, workshop design
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Universities (higher education)
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Students, young people

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Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Cross regional networking, higher education
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Higher education and networking – students (Digital Transformation in the Field of Education)
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Agenda development, invitation to the meeting: beginning of November meeting itself: end of November/beginning of December
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Application of digital communication ways for exchange with other students unions, to derive new ways of networking, new exchange environment, usability of digital territorials networking
Does that action support other goals?	Motivation for students to participate in the project.
Does that action support the realisation of other measures	Building up cross European capacities of digital natives, networking
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Science education, public engagement
Is that a cross territorial action	Yes, one need's the contact numbers of other Student Unions
Is it a single action or multiple?	Action consists of 3 steps s

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1	Establishing contact and developing a common agenda – hot topics on digital student exchange – new option of cooperation
2	Performing the exchange meeting – and outputs, new ideas of exchange
3	Report of the meeting, analysis and further perspectives, derive option to share results for the project amongst students, evaluation of the action

Action No 8: Digi@Lab

Name of action	Digi@Lab
Date (week or month)	Nov. 2021 – ongoing
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical Events, Leoben, Graz, Kapfenberg
Description of the action:	1.) Digital competences should be built up starting at kindergarten and primary school age. To support this, the following projects are to be initiated in the teaching-learning laboratory, which the Montanuniversitaet operates together with the Private University College of Teacher Education Augustinum (formerly KPH Graz):

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- Development of at least one workshop on the topic of robotics/coding for the age group of 5 to 11-year-olds:

Cooperation with the HTL Kapfenberg, which is designing a mini-robot that can be programmed by children in a playful way as part of a school project and is bringing it to series production readiness.

- Development of workshop content by Montanuniversität Leoben and PPH Augustinum in cooperation with HTL Kapfenberg
 - Development of accompanying pedagogical material by PPH Augustinum
 - Establishment of the workshops in the Teaching-Learning-Lab Leoben
 - Embedding of the developed contents in teacher training and further education by the PPH Augustinum

2.) Extension of the existing workshops (topics "raw materials/salts", "plastics", "metals (incl. magnetism)") by experiment stations with digital tools

- Playful teaching of digital skills to pupils as well as to teachers in vocational training and education (cooperation with PPH Augustinum).

Additional partners are to be brought on board for the projects, e.g., HTL Leoben and other educational institutions, companies. Dissemination is planned in cooperation with the Directorate of Education.

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Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Mag. Julia Mayerhofer-Lillie, Montanuniversitaet
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Education Institution, higher education and schools
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Schools, higher engineering schools, primary schools Higher education for training of teachers
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Knowledge and Skills
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Transformation in education system
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Start of action in November 2021, continuous till December 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Teachers have to be trained; topic were included in curricular recently Not sufficient general knowledge available, special knowledge has to be built up Access to excellent hardware for supporting learning process not always available
Does that action support other goals?	Building of networks and cooperation

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Does that action support the realisation of other measures	Design of environment, universal platform (Mai 2022-Dec. 2022)
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Science education
Is that a cross territorial action	No
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multipurpose action
1	3 Development of at least one workshop on the topic of robotics/coding for the age group of 5 to 11-year-olds (Nov 2021- September 2022)
2	Development of workshop content by Montanuniversitaet Leoben and PPH Augustinum in cooperation with HTL Kapfenberg (Nov 2021-Mai 2022)
3	Extension of the existing workshops (topics "raw materials/salts", "plastics", "metals (incl. magnetism)") by experiment stations with digital tools (Mai 2022-Dec. 2022) including evaluations

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Action No 9: Concept development “Styria Universal platform”

Name of action	Concept development “Styria Universal platform”
Date (week or month)	October 2021 – June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Online and physical workshops, concept development
Description of the action:	<p>The ultimate interface of all areas of life. It connects individual needs in terms of their social and cultural functions within society. It supports and guides through all areas of life from childcare to across all educational paths. Regional entrepreneurs find employees to match them or motivate people to train in specific niches before bottlenecks arise. A platform that respects ethical aspects of our society in the region and provides us with the information we need via depersonalized data in real time. It warns us of floods or avalanches and helps us to fulfil our duties as citizens and guides us through official regulations. A trusted platform for the whole region.</p> <p>The following aspects are considered separately:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological possibilities • Ethical aspects
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Julia Schmidbauer, Montanuniversitaet; Franz Edler, Centre for Applied Technology

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Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	All stakeholder in the region
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Mike Ulm, mea-IT Sonja Gögele, FH Joanneum
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Goal of interaction and cooperation, communication, network and collaboration
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	A universal platform for networking
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Start of the action will be in Oct. 2021
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	The gap of extensive possibility for interaction
Does that action support other goals?	An active, open culture that works together to the best of its ability, learning from each other and developing as a result.
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Map for educational institutions, job market, free-time activities

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	Image transformation of the region (increase immigration) Disaster management e-governance
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Public engagement, open access, ethical
Is that a cross territorial action	No
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multiple action
1 Elevate status, exchange with other	Learning from other: Oct. 2021 no platform in Styria available, Linz (19 th Oct. 21) has a digital strategy and an interactive homepage with a very workable design, analysis of other platforms
2 Develop a profile of the Stryrian platform	Workshop which features and functionality the platform should have
3 Exploring the technological possibilities	Two Half-day workshops are planned. The goal is a concept for the platform
4 Ethical aspects	In another half-day workshop, the ethical aspects will be critically reviewed

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Action No 10: Training on digital marketing in social media

Name of action	Is survival outside the digital market even possible? How far will it go?
Date (week or month)	December 2021 – June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Physical/Web-Stream
Description of the action:	Seminar with stakeholders from the Upper Styria region who are reluctant to digitize, despite all the signs on the market. How long can someone stay in such a market segment or will hybrid market strategies prevail. What are the dangers and opportunities of hybrid or purely web-based sales platforms? What scenarios are emerging on the digital market in the next 5 to 10 years. Trading at the bottom of reality in a digital world.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Franz Edler, Centre for Applied Technology
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Companies
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Entrepreneur, Tourism,

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	Brainsworld (Marketing), NiceShop (Online Shop)
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Leadership, Business & Market
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Technology and Knowledge Transfer, awareness, communication, knowledge and skills
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	December 2021 to June 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Market, structural barriers
Does that action support other goals	Public acceptance
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Digital transformation in field of education, creating work environments, universal platform
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Public engagement, ethics, open access, innovation
Is that a cross territorial action?	Not directly, but the concept of the training can be modified that it can be offered in the other DigiTeRRI Territories

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Is it a single action or multiple?	Multistep action
1	Establishing contact and developing a common agenda, promote and organize the event (Dec till April 2022)
2	Performing a seminar (April 2022)
3	Report of the meeting, analysis and further perspectives, derive option to share results for the project, questionnaire of the participant – mapping of WP5 (April till June 2022)

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Action No 11: Incubator exchange for fostering entrepreneurship in digitalisation

Name of action	Incubator exchange for fostering entrepreneurship in digitalisation
Date (week or month)	November 2021 –June 2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Web Event
Description of the action:	Develop digital awareness programs and encourage potential founders of their own start-up in a digital environment. Network interface between entrepreneurs with compatible interests and promote or support international market expansion efforts. Promoting digital processes in business management and technical cooperation between companies or expanding digital opportunities to ensure the economic strength of the regions. The cross regional Incubator network supports the development of the digital transformation of the regions through their collaboration and elaboration of risks & opportunities for young companies regarding sustainable growth strategies.
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Franz Edler (ZAT)
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Economy, research institutes

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If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Entrepreneurs, Start-up's, incubator
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Leadership, business & market, network and collaboration
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Platform for Networking
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	November 2021 – June 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	The gap of extensive possibility for interaction of incubators
Does that action support other goals?	Cross territory network, communication
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Technology transfer, creating work – environment and countering the lack of skilled labour and knowledge worker, interface of cross territorial markets
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Science education, ethics, open access Innovation, public engagement

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Is that a cross territorial action?	Incubators, Start-ups centres and entrepreneurs of all territories, network and knowledge transfer in all directions
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multiple action
1	Establishing contact and developing a common agenda, promote and organize the event
2	Performing the exchange meeting and seminars
3	Report of the meeting, analysis and further perspectives, derive option to share results for the project, questionnaire to the participants for mapping

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Action No 12: Cross Regional Event – B2B Networking event on industry and digitalisation

Name of action	B2B Networking event on industry and digitalisation
Date (week or month)	Preparation 11/2021 and 04/2022 Event 03/2022
Location (physical/web, event side)	Online /web
Description of the action:	<p>Stakeholders from Värmland, Styria, Grand Est should be invited for a one-day online event.</p> <p>Before the event the participants can give information about them and their interests on the event-homepage. Lectures guide the event.</p> <p>In Styria we would have available lectures about: digital transformation of small businesses, support through digitalisation for businesses The program will include the introduction of the DigiTeRRI project, the territories, some companies partner and the research organisations. For the digital event a registration platform will be set up, in which participating organisations can give their profile in advance and the individual exchange meetings on digitalisation can be performed The European Enterprise network will also be engaged.</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Brigitte Kriszt, Renate Reumüller, MUL

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	Värmland, Grand Est – to be nominated
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Industry Research, universities, education Government
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Speaker from industry and university, representatives of cities, regions, research organisation, companies
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Networks and collaboration Leadership, business & market, communication, technology
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Technology and knowledge transfer; cities, municipalities, public sector, countering the lack of skilled labour,
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	Preparation 11/2021 Event 02/2022 Analysis and outcome 4 /2020
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Cross regional learning and exchange, attracting other companies and partner for cooperation with the Styrian region in the field of application of digital solutions, offering new cooperation option to local companies

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Does that action support other goals?	Market expansion for companies and cooperation s Communication, culture and values
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Countering the lack of skilled labour force and knowledge worker
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	RRI oriented Innovation, anticipative, science education, public engagement, open access
Is it a single action or multiple?	Yes, Styria would take the lead in getting a benefit from the cooperation and exchange of the 3 DigiTeRRI territories. The process of stakeholder exchange and co-creation of innovation ideas and building European cooperation should be initiated.
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multi action initiative
1 Preparation	Drafting a concept for the online B2B event, getting in discussion with the other partner of DigiTeRRI, Decision on the software platform, designing the program, selection of speakers, initiate the cooperation with additional stakeholders
2 Performing the event	Dissemination and preparation of the meeting Dec 2021 -January 2022 ongoing, performing the event March 2022
3 Date collection for mapping	Analysis and evaluation – questionnaire to the attendances

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Action No 13: Plan Scan & Shop - explore the regional economy and important facilities online

Name of action	Scan & Shop - explore the regional economy and important facilities online
Date (week or month)	12/2021 – ongoing
Location (physical/web, event side)	physical link at shops, central facilities, etc. to an online platform – feature of the universal online platform, concept development
Description of the action:	<p>With graphically uniformly designed notices, which contain a QR code, on business areas, important facilities, etc., a link is made with underlying platforms, online shops, etc.</p> <p>This enables interested parties to obtain information, shop online, etc. at a low-threshold and outside of opening hours.</p> <p>Example: the city of Bruck an der Mur offers its businesses under "www.wirtschaft-bruckmur.at" a uniform platform with individual web presentations by the participating businesses. The ability to access information about the company or its online shop quickly and easily using a QR code at the store is intended to further increase its attractiveness.</p>
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	<p>Erich Weber</p> <p>Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur GesmbH</p>

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Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Citizens, economy, SME, industry
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Economy: Persons responsible for economic affairs at the municipal level. Entrepreneur Persons responsible for tourism and communal information. Civil society
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Leadership, business & market
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Platform for Networking
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	December 2021 – ongoing in 2022
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Low-threshold access to the topic of e-commerce and the associated expansion of these activities - also on the part of the company, if this enables new additional target groups to be tapped.

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Does that action support other goals	Infrastructure, communication,
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Technology and Knowledge Transfer
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Public engagement –getting transparency for public Giving open access
Is that a cross territorial action?	No
Is it a single action or multiple?	Concept development
	1 Analysis the number of companies which will take part, structure the segments
	2 Concept development for the platform – which information should be given – optional from profile of companies to the link to their online shopping platforms
	3 Integration of the scan & shop - explore the regional economy and important facilities online module in the universal platform

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Action No 14: Job platform for municipality co-workers

Name (kind) of action (short name)	Job platform for municipalities co-workers (competence profile in relation to digitalisation)
Date (week or month)	1/2022 – ongoing
Location (physical/web, event side)	Online / Web, discussion round, studies, concept development
Description of the action:	<p>Many communities are increasingly confronted with the problem of meeting their staffing needs - at all levels of education.</p> <p>In the past, the municipalities were in demand as employers because they offered secure long-term employment, but this picture has now changed. At the moment, the economy lures with significantly higher wages than the collective agreements of the municipalities allow. In addition, the attitude of the working population to the issue of "stability" has changed. A more frequent job change is valued differently now than it was a few years ago.</p> <p>New ways must therefore be found as to how municipalities can acquire their staff in the future and which measures can / must be taken in order to make these jobs more attractive.</p> <p>Ideas for this are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - common job platforms of municipalities - Personal pools

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	- Cross-community employment (e.g., lifeguard in summer and ice master in winter; at different communities), digital working environment
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Erich Weber Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur GesmbH
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Municipalities, citizen
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Persons responsible for employees matters at the municipal level.
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Networks & collaboration (Communication)s
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Cities, Municipalities, the Public Sector (Technology and Knowledge Transfer),
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	January 2022 – ongoing in 2022

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Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Creation of new access to the labour market.
Does that action support other goals?	Creating work-environments and countering the lack of skilled labour
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Cities, municipalities, public sector
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Public engagement, e- governance Anticipative, reflective, inclusive or responsive initiative
Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	Coordination with the transnational partners is currently taking place, as the Grand Est region may also be working on this topic.
Is it a single action or multiple?	Multiple actions
1	General clarification with the municipalities
2	Definition of the (technical) framework
3	Examination of cross-community employment measures

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Action No 15: Cultural Exchange – Step 1 Local Level

Name of action	Cultural exchange at the local level
Date (week or month)	1/2022 – ongoing
Location (physical/web, event side)	Online / Web
Description of the action:	<p>Development of a supra-regional exchange platform for cultural activities.</p> <p>There are different cultural activities in the cities and regions, although experience has shown that larger urban structures have more comprehensive offers than rural or geographically remote areas.</p> <p>The aim is to offer the existing cultural initiatives (music schools, theatres, etc.) a platform where they can make their performances online to a broader base.</p> <p>Example: during the lockdown as a result of COVID19, the music school Bruck an der Mur put videos of the home rehearsals of the music students online and thus brought the music to those interested in art. Building on this idea, a model for supra-regional cultural exchange is to be developed. The outcome of the activities should be integrated in the universal platform concept. It is planned to link distance cultural events of the other territories to the action of the Styrian territory</p>

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Who is responsible for that the performance of that action	Erich Weber Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur GesmbH
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address	Cultural institutions, municipalities, citizens
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation	Persons responsible for cultural affairs at the municipal level. Companies with know-how and infrastructure for the (professional) processing of audio-visual contributions. Artists Other territory members of the DigiTeRRI consortium
Action belongs to which objects/goal in the territorial roadmap	Culture & values
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes	Universal platform, cities, municipalities, citizens, public authorities
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)	January 2022 – ongoing in 2022

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Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap	Use of digital resources to disseminate art & culture and make the associated possibilities visible.
Does that action support other goals?	Communication
Does that action support the realisation of other measures?	Universal platform
Which RRI dimension/keys/processes are addressed?	Public engagement Giving open access
Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories	The concept would be suitable for cross-territorial action, but appropriate discussions must first be held for this.
Is it a single action or multiple actions	Single action

APPENDIX 1

The actions were collected with the following template.

Name of action
Date (week or month)
Location (physical/web, event side)
Description of the action:
Who is responsible for that the performance of that action
Name Target group(s) within quadruple helix according to groups in D3.1 the action will address
If stakeholders are involved give the name and type of their organisation
Action belongs to which objectives/goal in the territorial roadmap
Name the group of measure to which the action contributes
Timeline for action preparation (when should the action be performed beginning of preparation)
Describe the impact of action – which gap will be closed according to the territorial roadmap
Does that action support other goals? Name them
Does that action support the realisation of other measures? – name them
Which RRI dimension/key/processes are addressed? Anticipative, reflective, inclusive or responsive initiative Address one of the keys (gender equality, science education, public engagement, ethics, giving open access, RRI governance)
Is that a cross territorial action, if yes, describe what kind of cooperation and exchange will be needed from the other DigiTeRRI territories
Is it a single action or multiple actions (add lines for each event)? Please describe, which actions will have to follow.
Sub activity 1
Sub activity 2
Sub activity 3